

FORM THE MOTIVATION OF CREATIVE ACTIVITY IN STUDENTS PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS.

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Anotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada talabalarda ijodiy faollik motivatsiyasi faoliyat haqida tushuncha psixologik xususiyatlari motivatsiya jarayoning umumiy tushunchalari o`quv faoliyatining ko`nikma bilim majmuyi jarayonlari haqida Motiv faoliyatga undovchi sabab. Maqsad istalgan, ya`ni, faoliyatni bajarish bilan erishiladigan natijaning tasviri bo`yicha amalga oshiradigan ishlar tahlili haqida fikr mulohazalar keltirilgan.

Kalit so`zlar: Faoliyat, subyekt, psixik tasvir, motivatsiya, predmetli harakatlar, tashqi faoliyat, real shart sharoit, predmetlar xususiyatlari, oddiy akt, psixologik jarayon.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются творческая деятельность студентов, мотивация, понимание деятельности, психологические особенности, общие понятия о процессе мотивации, о процессах учебной деятельности, набор умений, мотивационная причина деятельности. Приводятся мнения об анализе выполненной работы по образцу желаемой цели, т. е. результата, достигаемого выполнением деятельности.

Key words: Activity, subject, mental image, motivation, actions with objects, external activity, real conditions, characteristics of objects, simple act, psychological process.

Annotation: In this article, students' creative activity, motivation, understanding of activity, psychological characteristics, general concepts of the motivation process, about the processes of the educational activity, the skill set, the motivational reason for activity. Opinions are given about the analysis of the work

performed according to the image of the desired goal, i.e., the result achieved by the performance of the activity.

Ключевые слова: Деятельность, субъект, психический образ, мотивация, действия с предметами, внешняя деятельность, реальные условия, характеристики предметов, простое действие, психологический процесс.

Activity is a developing system of the subject's interaction with the world. In the process of such interaction, a mental image is formed and its expression in the object, as well as the subject's realization of his relationship with reality. Any simple act of activity is a form of expression of the subject's activity, which means that each activity has motivational reasons and is directed to achieve certain results. Any activity in real conditions, in different ways and in different ways. manifests itself in appearances. Since every action is aimed at a certain thing - an object, the activity is imagined as a set of actions with an object. Actions with objects are aimed at changing the properties and quality of objects in the external world. For example, the subject action of a student summarizing a lecture is focused on writing, and he is enriching the stock of knowledge by first of all changing the number and quality of entries in that notebook. External and internal activities are distinguished, depending on what exactly the activity and the objective actions that make up it are aimed at. External activity is an activity aimed at changing the external environment surrounding a person and things and events in it, while internal activity is primarily a mental activity, which results from the passage of purely psychological processes. From the point of view of origin, internal - mental, psychic activity originates from activity with an external object. At first, external activity with an object takes place, as experience is gained, these actions gradually turn into internal mental processes. If we take this as an example of speech activity, the child expresses the first words with a loud sound in his external speech, later he learns to speak on his own, thinks, reflects, sets goals and

plans for himself. goes on. In any situation, all actions are controlled by the mind, both from the point of view of internal-psychological and external-consistency. Any activity includes both mental and physical - motor actions. For example, have you ever observed a wise man thinking? If you carefully observe a thinking person, although the leading activity in him is mental, his forehead, eyes, even the movements of his body and hands are not able to settle on a very important and serious thought, or find a new idea and take it from him. shows that he is happy. At first glance, the actions of a gardener who performs external elementary work - for example, ridding a grape seedling of excess leaves, are also not without mental components. The term "motivation" has a wider meaning than the term "motive". The word "motivation" is the determining factor of behavior in modern psychology. For this, in particular, it is used in a double sense as a feature of the motivating process, which determines the system of needs, motives, goals, aspirations and many others) and keeps behavioral activity at a certain level. We use the concept of motivation in the first sense. Thus, motivation can be defined as a set of psychological reasons that explain human behavior, its origin, direction and activity. The flexibility of the motivational field characterizes the motivation process as follows: for the satisfaction of a higher motivational inclination, various lower levels the more different motivational tendencies are used, the more flexible the motivational domain. For example, if one individual's need for knowledge is satisfied only through television, radio, and movies, for another, the means of satisfying the same need are various books, periodicals, and communication with people. In the latter case, the motivational field is considered more flexible. In addition to motives, needs and goals, interests, problems, wishes and goals are also considered as drivers of human behavior. Curiosity refers to a specific motivational state that has the character of knowing, is not directly connected with the same, current need. The problem arises when the organism encounters obstacles that need to be overcome while performing an action aimed at achieving a certain goal.

Desires and goals are immediate and often interchangeable motivational subjective states that respond to changes in the conditions of action. Knowing the nature of motives and the problem of changing them is important in studying the motivations of various professions. One of these motivations is to achieve success in various fields of activity

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